

4Q35 (4QDeut^h) frag. 1 (IAA Plate 389, frag. 1) + PAM 43.686 frag. 7 (IAA Plate 18, frag. 4)

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The hitherto unidentified Qumran Cave 4 fragment PAM 43.686 frag. 7 (DJD 33, 197) joins materially and textually to the left of 4Q35 frag. 1 lines 13-14 (cf. DJD 14, 63).

Fig. 1: 4Q35 frag. 1 + PAM 43.686 frag. 7 (bottom left)

screen captures from

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-298249>

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-508161>

PAM 43.686 frag. 7 preserves the bottom parts of all four letters of 4Q35 frag. 1 line 13 פנים, and the last word of 4Q35 frag. 1 line 14 ושמעתיו.

Fig. 2: PAM 43.686 frag. 7 (IAA Plate 18, frag. 4)

screen capture from

<https://www.deadseascrolls.org.il/explore-the-archive/image/B-501029>

One may now transcribe the preserved part of lines 13-14 follows (Deuteronomy 1:16-17)

ושפ[טתם צדק בין איש ובין אחיו ובין גרו לא תכירו פנים	13
לאלה[ים הוא והדבר אשר יקשה מכם תקריבון אלי ושמעתיו	14

On the basis of the photographs it is not possible to determine whether the dark dot above the final *waw* of ושמעתיו is ink or not. Note, however, that on the photographs of the preserved fragments of 4Q35, there are many smaller and larger darker dots, and that the positioning of the dot just above the *waw* need not be intentional.

References:

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| DJD 14 | Eugene Ulrich et al., <i>Qumran Cave 4, IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 14 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995) |
| DJD 33 | Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, <i>Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments</i> , Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001) |
| IAA | Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). Fragment numbers are those given by the IAA in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il |
| PAM | Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs) |